

Effects of Tartrazine Subchronic Ingestion on Brush Border Membrane Enzymes of Female Swiss Albino Mice Intestine

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ABSTRACT

Background: Tartrazine is a food colour that possesses adverse health effect to human such as hyperactivity in children, allergy and asthma. However, its effect on intestinal enzymes activity is not been established. Materials and methods: Tartrazine was administered to female swiss albino mice in drinking water at doses of 0.45% and 1% for 13 weeks. Mucosal scrape samples of the jejunum were collected for disaccharidases and dipeptidases activity analyses. Results: Maltase, sucrase and lactase specific activities were lower particularly in groups treated with 1% Tartrazine. Similarly, total and specific activities of L-leucyl-L-alanine, L-alanyl-L-proline and L-glycyl-L-proline dipeptidase are decreased in both treated groups. Villus height and crypt depth were decreased also in the same groups. Conclusion: the subchronic ingestion of Tartrazine at 0.45% and 1% in mice modifies disaccharidases and dipeptidases activities as well as intestine histological structure, thus it affects intestine function.

Keywords: Tartrazine, disaccharidases, dipeptidases, intestinal structure, mice.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial colorants are found in thousands of food products¹⁻⁶. In particular breakfast cereals, candy, snacks, beverages and other products aimed at children are colored with dyes. Synthetic colorants are approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for use in foods, pharmaceuticals and cosmetic preparations.

Some of artificial colorants like Tartrazine pose a potential risk to human health, especially if they are excessively consumed⁷⁻²². The acceptable daily intake (ADI) for human is 0-7.5 mg kg⁻¹ body weight²³ but almost children exceed their ADI^{24,25,26}.

Several experimental studies have been conducted on Tartrazine demonstrated that among the biochemical systems which are likely to be affected by the ingestion of this food color is the oxidative stress because of its role in tissue damage. The mechanisms might be attributed to promoting lipid peroxidation products and reactive oxygen species, inhibiting endogenous antioxidant defense enzymes^{12,15,19,27}. Oxidative stress is believed to be one important cause of gastrointestinal inflammation, ulcer and colitis²⁸.

The brush border (BB) membrane lining the epithelial cells of small intestine is one of the most important cellular membranes owing to its role in the digestion and absorption of nutrients. Due to this dual function the membrane contains a number of hydrolytic enzymes and transport system²⁹. The BB enzymes are crucial for the functioning of the intestine. It is well documented that dietary modification is correlated with significant changes in histology and biochemistry of the small intestine³⁰. The

study of Guendouz *et al.*³¹ demonstrated that subchronic ingestion of Tartrazine at doses of 0.45% and 1% induced villous atrophy and inflammation of the intestine. Moreover, BB enzymes activities may be affected. Thus the aim of this study is to investigate the disaccharidase and dipeptidase activities following subchronic Tartrazine ingestion.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals

The chemical name of the colorant is Tartrazine also known as (FD & C Yellow No. 5, C.I. No. 19140, and Food Yellow No. 4). The purity of this azo dye is 86.6%, it was provided from Dyechem, Morocco. The bovine serum albumine was purchased from Biochem (UK). Glucose oxydase, peroxydase, glucose, glycine, L- Leucyl-Alanine, L- Alanyl- Proline L- Glycyl- Proline dipeptides, lactose and sucrose were purchased from Sigma (USA). Alanine, maltose, Folin reagent and ninhydrin were purchased from Merck (Germany).

Animals and treatments

All animals were used following the instructions of Oran University guidelines for animal use. Thirty swiss albino female mice aged of 4 weeks old and weighing (12.85±0.26) g obtained from Pasteur institute, Algiers, Algeria, were kept under proper conditions of ambient temperature and adequate humidity. Tartrazine was diluted in water. Mice were divided into three groups, each one including 10 females. The first group was given drinking water as a control group, the second group was given drinking water containing 0.45% of Tartrazine (presents

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the no observed adverse effect levels (NOAEL)^{32,33} and the third one was given drinking water containing 1% of Tartrazine (high dose) for a period of 13 weeks. Standard food pellets diet and water were given *ad libitum* for the duration of the experiment. Food and liquid consumption were measured daily and mean daily intake of tartrazine (mg/kg/day) during the administration period was calculated. Body weight was measured weekly.

After 13 weeks of administration, the animals were fasted for 18 hours and sacrificed on the day of necropsy by cervical dislocation. The small intestine was removed and its contents were flushed thoroughly with cold saline. The jejunum was then divided into two segments; one was excised for biochemical assays and the second for histological assessment.

Samples preparation

The mucosa was scraped with two glass slides onto an ice-chilled glass plate and then weighed. After, the mucosa was homogenized in cold Ringer (1000 μ L/30 mg tissue) with a Potter-Elvehjem glass on ice for 3 minutes. The homogenate was used for enzyme determinations and protein content.

Protein determination

The protein concentration was determined according to the method of Lowry *et al.*³⁴ using Bovine serum albumin as standard.

Disaccharidases activities

Lactase (EC 3.2.1.23), maltase (EC 3.2.1.20) and sucrase (EC 3.2.1.48) activities were determined using the method of Dahlqvist³⁵. Homogenate was diluted with cold Ringer solution. Diluted samples of homogenate (20 μ l) were pipetted into glass tubes for measurement disaccharidase activities with addition of an appropriate substrate (20 μ l) diluted in a maleate buffer (pH 6.0). The mixture was incubated at 37°C for 60 min. The content of released glucose was determined using the enzymatic glucose oxidase by adding 600 μ l of solution (glucose oxidase, peroxidase, triton x100, O-dianisidine, tris buffer pH 7.0). The mixture was incubated at 37°C for 35 min. Absorbance was determined using a spectrophotometer (UV/vis; JASCO V-530, Japan) set at 340-480 nm. The results were expressed as μ mol glucose/min/g of tissue. The liberated glucose is measured, along with the total protein concentration of the homogenate. The specific activities of each enzyme are reported in units of μ mol/min/g protein.

Dipeptidases activities

L- glycyl- L- proline, L-alanyl- L- proline and L-Leucyl- L-Alanine dipeptidases activities were measured by Doi *et al.*³⁶ method in homogenized jejuna mucosa. Dipeptidases were determined using appropriate substrates and the amino acid released was determined using the ninhydrin colorimetric method. The results were expressed as μ mol of amino acids/min/g of tissue and specific activities of each enzyme are reported in units of μ mol/min/g protein.

Histological assessment

Small jejunum segments of 3 cm were removed and fixed in 10% formalin overnight. Paraffin-embedded, samples were sliced to approximately 4 μ m with a microtome, mounted on slides, and stained with hematoxylin and

eosin. Approximately 40 Villi heights and crypt depths of each animal were measured at 10 \times magnification using a Nikon microscope and Optiphot-2 software.

Statistical analysis

The data was expressed as mean \pm SE. Statistical test one way ANOVA was applied to find significant difference between values of various parameters recorded for control and treated animals. *P* values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Body weights, food and liquid consumption

The average of the final body weight gain, daily Food and liquid consumption through the administration period are shown in table 1.

No significant changes occur in final body weight gain and food consumption in experimental groups compared to controls. However, liquid consumption values were significantly increased at all experimental groups compared to controls ($p < 0.05$).

Disaccharidase activities

Total activities of maltase and sucrase in the jejunum were not significantly reduced in treated groups compared to control group (figure 1A and figure 3A), but their specific activities were significantly decreased in 1% tartrazine treated groups ($p < 0.01$) (figure 1B and figure 3B). In addition, the specific activity of sucrase was also significantly reduced in 0.45% tartrazine treated groups compared to controls ($p < 0.05$) (figure 3B).

Jejunal total activity of lactase was significantly reduced in mice treated with 1% of tartrazine ($p < 0.01$) (figure 2A). Whereas, its specific activity was significantly decreased in 0.45% ($p < 0.01$) and 1% tartrazine treated groups ($p < 0.01$) compared to controls (figure 2B).

Dipeptidase activities

The total and specific activities of all dipeptidases studied were depressed in the jejunum of treated mice with different doses of tartrazine.

Regarding both total and specific activities of L-leucyl-L-alanine and L-alanyl-L-proline dipeptidases were significantly decreased in all treated groups ($p < 0.01$) compared to the control groups (figure 4 and figure 6). Similarly, total and specific activities of L-glycyl-L-proline dipeptidase were significantly decreased in 0.45% and 1% treated groups ($p < 0.05$) and ($p < 0.01$) respectively compared to controls (figure 5).

Villus height and crypt depth

Histological analysis of the jejunum in mice treated with tartrazine showed that increasing dietary tartrazine concentrations alter villus height and crypt depth (table 2). Shorter villi were observed in the jejunum of mice treated with tartrazine compared to controls. In the same time, crypt depth was also decreased significantly in both treated groups compared to control group ($p < 0.01$).

DISCUSSION

The objective of this study was to measure the disaccharidase and dipeptidase activities following subchronic Tartrazine ingestion at dose of 0.45% and 1%.

Table 1: Effect of tartrazine ingestion on body weight gain.

Groups (g)	Initial BW(g)	Final BW(g)	Gain BW(g)
Controls	12.95±0.58	34.48±0.88	21.55±0.39
0.45%	12.82±0.35	34.11±0.82	21.29±0.86
1%	12.80±0.38	33.78±0.72	20.98±0.40 ^{NS}

Values represent mean ±SE of ten mice (n = 10).
 NS: no significantly different (ANOVA test).

Table 2: Daily intake of fluid containing tartrazine and food for 13 weeks.

Groups	Food intake(g)	Fluid intake(ml)	Daily intake of tartrazine mg/kg/day
Controls	5.88±0.39	4.46±0.20	000.00
0.45%	5.94±0.42	5.75±0.42 ^a	839.42
1%	6.47±0.46	5.25±0.35 ^a	1625.99

Values represent mean ±SE of ten mice (n = 10).
 Means which have letters are significantly different, P<0.05 (ANOVA test).

Figure 1: Effect of tartrazine on maltase activities in mice. Values represent mean ±SE of ten mice (n = 10). Means which have letters are significantly different, (a) significant versus control (P<0.01).

Figure 2: Effect of tartrazine on lactase activities in mice. Values represent mean ±SE of ten mice (n = 10). Means which have letters are significantly different, (a) significant versus control (P<0.05) and (P<0.01) respectively.

Figure 3: Effect of tartrazine on sucrase activities in mice. Values represent mean \pm SE of ten mice ($n = 10$). Means which have letters are significantly different, (a) significant versus control ($P < 0.05$) and ($P < 0.01$) respectively.

Figure 4: Effect of tartrazine on L-Leu-Ala dipeptidase activities in mice. Values represent mean \pm SE of ten mice ($n = 10$). Means which have letters are significantly different, (a) significant versus control ($P < 0.01$).

Figure 5: Effect of tartrazine on L-Gly-Pro dipeptidase activities in mice. Values represent mean \pm SE of ten mice ($n = 10$). Means which have letters are significantly different, (a) significant versus control ($P < 0.05$) and ($P < 0.01$) respectively, (b) significant versus 0.45% ($P < 0.01$).

Figure 6: Effect of tartrazine on L-Ala-L-Pro dipeptidases activities in mice. Values represent mean \pm SE of ten mice ($n = 10$). Means which have letters are significantly different, (a) significant versus control ($P < 0.01$), (b) significant versus 0.45% ($P < 0.05$).

The body weight gain decreases in treated groups in spite of high food intakes in 1% tartrazine groups. These results are in accordance with the study of Guendouz *et al.*³¹ and the study of Amin *et al.*¹² which showed that oral administration of high (500 mg/kg bw) or low (15 mg/kg bw) doses of Tartrazine decreased significantly the body weight gain in young male rats. Fluid intake is higher in both experimental groups. Different studies showed an increased consumption of tartrazine in diet by rats or mice^{37,38,11}. It seems that tartrazine increases the appetency, could it possibly addiction.

Disaccharidases such maltase, sucrase and lactase localize in the BB membrane of small intestinal mucosa, but not in the digestive fluid. The hydrolyzing activity is highest at the proximal jejunum and decreases toward the distal ileum³⁹. The hydrolyzing activities are measured extensively in humans and experimental animals⁴⁰⁻⁴⁶.

In the present study, we have shown that intestinal disaccharidase specific activities are lower in groups treated with 0.45% and 1% Tartrazine. However, maltase specific activity was only decreased in group treated with 1%. In under normal conditions, this level of activity is controlled by the abundance of the mRNA encoding the proteins^{47,48}. In situ hybridization analysis of rat jejunum revealed that sucrase mRNA levels were maximal in lower and mid-villus cells with lower levels observed in the villus tip⁴⁹. Lactase mRNA levels were also detected in the villus cells of rat jejunum⁵⁰.

The BB disaccharidases, lactase and sucrase are considered accurate markers of enterocyte maturity and functional capacity^{51,52}. It has been reported that dietary modification is associated with altered activity of the BB disaccharidases³⁰, such as Zn deficiency^{53,54,44}, iron deficiency⁵⁵, and vitamin A deficiency⁵⁶. Zn and iron deficiencies have been reported by Ward *et al.*⁵⁷ (1990) and Ward⁵⁸ in hyperactive children consuming food additives such Tartrazine. Further researches are needed to determine the mineral status of animals exposed to Tartrazine.

Dipeptidases are also a membrane bound enzymes, anchored to the membrane of the enterocytes, their activities may also be compromised and may have occasioned their observed low activities in jejunum of Tartrazine treated mice. The effect of Tartrazine on dipeptidases in the proximal end of the small intestine would severely compromise protein digestion and thus its availability.

The measurements of villus height and crypt depth provide an indication of the maturity and the functional capacity of small intestinal enterocytes. Our results have demonstrated that Tartrazine ingestion markedly decreased villus height and crypt depth in mice treated with 0.45% and 1%. Similar results were obtained by Guendouz *et al.*³¹.

The BB lining the surface of the small intestinal epithelium provides the major interface for nutrient absorption. Reduction in the surface area of the microvilli is linked with impaired levels of disaccharidase enzymes such as sucrase and lactase that are essential for proper digestion and absorption of sugars²⁹.

Disaccharidase deficiency can result from numerous situations such as intestinal infection or inflammation. Jejunal inflammation (immune cell hyperplasia) associated with villus atrophy in mice treated with 0.45% and 1% tartrazine were noted in the study of Guendouz *et al.*³¹. They attributed inflammatory cell infiltration to an active chronic jejunitis. This lesion destroys the mucous membrane and can even stretch the mucosa layer⁵⁹. Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* investigations show that uncontrolled synthesis of pro-inflammatory cytokines can have a strong influence on gut integrity and epithelial functions including permeability to macromolecules and transport of nutrients and ions⁶⁰.

In our study, the decrease of disaccharidase and dipeptidase activities is correlated with the decrease of villus height. Our results are consistent with previous reports describing a strong relation with low level of dipeptidase activity and villus atrophy^{61,42}. Our data suggest that the decrease is likely due to a decline in enzyme protein rather than an inactivation of the enzyme

Table 3: Villus height and Crypt depth of jejunum in mice 13 weeks.

Groups	Villus height (µm)	Crypt depth (µm)
Controls	46.70±0.40	12.44±0.60
0.45%	24.92±1.31 ^a	8.02±0.75 ^a
1%	16.04±0.67 ^{a,b}	6.00±0.90 ^{a,b}

Values represent mean ±SE of ten mice ($n = 10$). Means which have letters are significantly different, $P < 0.01$ (ANOVA test).

activity. Further studies are necessary for determining the origin of these intestinal alterations.

In conclusion, our results suggest that subchronic ingestion of Tartrazine at 0.45% (equivalents to 839 mg/kg/day) and at high dose 1% (equivalents to 1626 mg/kg/day) decreases markedly jejunal disaccharidases particularly sucrase and lactase and dipeptidases as well as alters intestine structure and the body weight loss. Indeed, the excessive consumption of food products containing Tartrazine may contribute to affect the intestine function and integrity.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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